

Research Article

Spatial Model of Customer Lifetime Value

Abdul Manaf Bohari¹, and Nurwahida Fuad²

¹ Associate Profesor, School of Business Management, Universiti Utara Malaysia; manafdr@uum.edu.my

² Senior Lecturer, Faculty of Business Management, Universiti Teknologi MARA, UiTM Kampus Arau, Perlis; wahida.fuad@uitm.edu.my

* Correspondence: manafdr@uum.edu.my; 0192986828

Abstract: *Developing a Spatial model of Customer Lifetime Value (CLV) by using Geographical Information Systems (GIS) is a new approach in the area of business management. Fundamentally, CLV functionally for estimating the profitability of the business, as indicates of how long the business can survive in the geographical marketplaces. The grassroots issues of CLV related model and approach, as referred by the four major approaches of CLV, there are limited work and knowledge on how to measure CLV based on spatial point of view. The aim of this project is to develop a Spatial Model of Customer Lifetime Value (SCLV), using the hybrid approach of Geographical Information Systems (GIS) and survey, with aimed for enhance the capabilities of prospecting customers' profitability for hypermarket businesses. The topmost CLV model as identified as Recency, Frequency and Monetary (RFM) model were transforming into the spatial based RFM, and then the spatial visualization of spatial RFM will be based on geographical marketplace as identified as Seberang Perai Tengah of Penang. This study contributes on the new method and theory on how to improve the accuracy of CLV specifically on free customer profitability. The Spatial Model of Customer Lifetime Value (SCLV) becomes a major method where its application will be spreads in many sector of industries. They are big potential for SCLV as commercials product by next development of SCLV apps version as possible to use by many type of business especially small and medium business.*

Keywords: Customer Lifetime Value; Geographical Information Systems; Spatial Model of Customer Lifetime Value.

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Managing the customer value (CV) is the top one initiative to ensure the sustainability of firms' profitability, both short and long term of performances, as mentioned by recent scholars such as Ali and Shabn (2024), Amendah, et al. (2023), Bauer and Jannach (2021), and many more. It is critical to understand and sustain the CV as well as business profitability, where it is important to a lifetime of business survival. Recently, Eileen (2008) noted that to maximise long-term returns of the company, customer's value must be managed so as to move in the same direction as customer profitability. Berman and Evans (2007) have discussed some issues on profitability which included how the business can best serve the customers while retaining fair profits; how the business stand out in a highly competitive environment where consumers have so many choices; and how the business grow up their business while retaining a core of loyal customers. Thereby, customer is a source of CV and profitability where they have power to revolutionize their relationships to the business (Fabel et al., 2008) and because of consequences of consumers intensely value-oriented, even more than in the recent past (Janiak, 2009).

Managing customer is important for retail business such as hypermarket store because of many reasons, but mostly related to the business profitability. Scholars like Hamit (2011); Peter (2010); Fader (2009); Epstein, et al. (2008); Gilbert (2007); Berger, et al. (2006); Adams (2005); Ching, et al. (2004); Bell, et al. (2002); Berger and Nasr (1998), and many more concern the important contribution of CV toward business profitability. In principles, customer is an asset to the business as described by Gupta and Lehmann (2003) and for that, the business must know how to value their customers that contributes their business performance (Gupta, et al. 2004). In this way, Glady, et al. (2009) stressed that customers are important assets to the business that must have to be precisely valued. From the research work of these scholars, CV is summarized as an important factor that must be evaluated, mostly by applying the Customer Lifetime Value (CLV) model and approach.

Since the CLV has been introduced to the field in the 1930s especially on marketing/retailing research, a multitude of CLV approaches have emerged, with variation in definitions, terms, and analogies (Graf & Maas, 2008). Specifically, there are two main streams of theoretical differentiable approaches for CLV, identified as CLV from a company perspective and CLV from a customer's perspective. However, both approaches have limitations on spatial capability that been used for estimating the profitability of business.

Traditionally, CLV model is mostly developed based on financial, accounting or consumer purchasing based instruments. In the firm-based CLV model, CLV is developed based on accounting or financial based measurement with high consideration on items such as costs, expenses, investment, rate, and any kind of tangible values that was cited in major works of Rust, et al. (2004); Gupta and Zeithaml (2006); Gupta, et al. (2006); and Bejou, et al. (2007). In contrast to the perspective of customer-based CLV model, CLV is more on customer-related behavior purchasing activity, such as recency, frequency, and monetary instruments, as described as RFM model by Libey (1998). Similarly, both perspectives are modelled either based on mathematical or statistical modelling with finale aim to estimate the profitability customers to the business. However, all of CLV models are not applicable to visualize the CLV results in term of spatial location, as customer located in the geographical marketplace.

Modelling the CLV of customer should be aligned with modelling the customers and marketplace where the traditional CLV model is not in capability. Technically, most of the CLV traditional model have had emphasized on costing for estimating the sustaining of profitability of the business, for example the Gamma/Gamma sub model by Fader, et al. (2005); and Customer Pathing model by Lenskold (2003). However, these models are not aligned with the current changes in marketplace as latest information are not be able to integrated into the CLV model. As evident, the increasing price on customer product and its implications to frequency and monetary value of purchasing on the side of customer is out-off prediction of any CLV model as reported by Hillier and Karki (2008). Consequently, the traditional CLV model has less advantage to be applied depending on the change of marketplaces.

The traditional CLV model as well as financial/account types models, CRM/marketing type's models, operation/decision science types models and ICT/Computer science based models consistently apply financial or accounting related instruments. For example, Customer Segment Knowledge Model by Ha and Bae (2006) has utilized financial based instruments, but does not support any analysis related to location of customer. In fact, non-financial instrument such as accessibility and location can affect the profitability of business as mentioned in some work of Carpenter and Moore (2006); Bromley and Matthews (2007); and Andronikov (2008). This is also supported by Wang, et al. (2008) as they noted that predicting the CLV of a customer requires several related factors to location. The predicted problem is transformed to a problem of creating a mapping function having all related features as its variables. Thus, according to these scholars, new technique must be introduced for modelling the CLV by integrating the non-financial variables into it.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

Methodically, a combination of GIS-survey methods is used in this study where it involves two types of data, that is, spatial and non-spatial data. Non-spatial data are processed and converted into spatial and attributes data first before they are combined with spatial data. In fact, spatialization process is applied to non-spatial data to transform it to a suitable format which is spatial format. Meanwhile, some procedures are applied and or developed by the researcher to integrate the spatial and non-spatial data into a platform of GIS.

2.1 Non-Spatial Variables

For this study, RFM model will apply to non-database customer, which is done by calculating on individual value, as applied by related studies of RFM model. In formula, RFM is represented in equation as below:

$$CLV = R \times F \times M$$

Where,

R = the latest purchase amount.

F = the total number of purchases during a specific period.

M = monetary value spent during one specific period.

Technically, Kumar and Reintz (2006) mentioned that one of the methods used for computing the RFM value is involves the computation of relative weights for each R, F, and M. For this study, this option was applied where the RFM database of free customer was established first, as sources from the survey data. The establishment of free customer database has a similar function to the CRM traditional database.

2.2 Spatial and Tabular Data

Basically, the development of GIS conceptual model of SCLV will comprise spatial and non-spatial data. Basically, the common spatial data are boundary, road and street, mukim, residential area, and so on. It is important to develop the physical side of geographical marketplace of the study. Meanwhile, specific spatial data were developed by the researcher. They are related to items or variables that were used in the questionnaires. Spatial data that were used for developing the geographical marketplace of Seberang Perai Tengah (SPT). With regard to geographical marketplace of SPT, a spatial data related to section of demographic background and hypermarket selection and CLV were also needed.

The softwares chosen for the study were ArcView, ArcGIS, Google Earth Pro/Google Add, Statch Map, iTouchMap (online coordinate software), SPSS and Excell. The main software used was ArcView which was suitable for the purposes of the study to develop a model, design layers and database. GIS software was used for mapping and developing spatial model, as well as for modelling the spatial data and performing the spatialization process from non-spatial to spatial data. Meanwhile, SPSS and Excell were used for processing the data from the survey as well as for developing the database of free customer, performing statistical analysis and testing the variables.

In order to modelling the CLV spatial data, vector model was utilized to model the data. As discussed before in chapter 2, vector data models the information about points, lines, and polygons as x, y coordinate. As example of modelling, the postal address needs to be in points based data. In this study, some procedures were developed and applied to perform these duties, which will be explained, accordingly in the chapter. In addition, for the non-spatial data, the conversion process is

vital where raw data from survey will be converted to the tabular form. The transformation of non-spatial into spatial data is for make the data available to integrate with spatial data.

2.3 Spatial Database Development

In order to develop a database of SCLV, various datasets representing spatial and non-spatial activities of the study need to be integrated based on database method. Basically, digital basic data, as described before, were upgraded on its attributes according to the requirement of the study. This is because it is possible that current spatial data is out-of-date and less concurrent, as well as less complete, according to the current status of the data as in the real situation.

The non-spatial data, survey was developed based on section of the questionnaires. These tabular data were used with spatial data, where it was possible to integrate via some procedures, as such geo reference, geo coding, and spatial joint procedures. With regard to spatial and non-spatial data, the whole process of conversion and integration of spatial and non-spatial data is applied in the project.

2.4 Location of the Study

Seberang Perai especially Seberang Perai Tengah (SPT) was chosen as a location of the study with some reasons as mentioned in literature review. Basically, Seberang Perai is part of the Penang state situated in a narrow hinterland opposite Penang Island in the Northern part of Malay Peninsular. Seberang Perai lies wholly between 5° 5' 00" N and 5° 35' 00" N latitude and it covers from East to West longitude of 100° 20' 00" E and 100° 35' 00" E. The other towns in the Seberang Perai area include Butterworth, Bukit Mertajam, Seberang Jaya, Sungai Puyu, Prai, Nibong Tebal, Juru, and Kepala Batas. In addition, SPT is surrounded by urbanization, with modern infrastructures and info-structure. It is the major centre for the modernization of the whole of Seberang Perai.

Basically, the Seberang Perai Tengah of Pulau Pinang in Malaysia is chosen as a location of study for some reasons. Firstly, Seberang Perai Tengah is a centre of development of Seberang Perai where it places main sector of business, government, private, and infrastructure. This is similar to Narimah (2002) whereby Seberang Perai area, including Seberang Perai Tengah has currently developed rapidly since 1970s. One of the reasons is that urban development in Seberang Perai was mainly due to industrialization and spill-over demand from Penang Island. It is located in the strategic location of the Northern Region of Peninsular Malaysia. Therefore, with regard to Narimah, SPT is a heart of the Northern Region of Peninsular Malaysia that might potentially represent the latest trend and future prospect of the North area.

The second reason for the selection of the area is the availability of hypermarkets and other related retailing business, in a huge number compared to the total population of Seberang Perai itself. Meaning that this area will be more interesting for testing the latest version lifetime model that can estimate how long the business can survive. The third reason is Seberang Perai contains various ethnic and religion, where is has potentially to represent Malaysian study of CLV. Because of each ethnic group has different fresh food consumption and usage, even differs in many aspects, this area is challenging for the study where analysis by individual RFM will be hard to compare to normal customer.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Geographical Marketplace of Seberang Perai Tengah

The physical aspect of the study area requires compressing the spatial data which consist of the boundary of SPT, basically, includes the Mukim and residential areas, recreation parks, as well as residential areas within the SP population, which are available in polygon-based data. The spatial

data of street and road systems including the highways are also important to represent the location of free customers which are available in line-based data. In addition, the spatial data of major towns in SP, as well as Seberang Jaya, Butterworth, Sungai Dua, Kepala Batas, Bukit Mertajam, Juru, Jawi, Permatang Pauh, and Perai are visualized in point-based data. Locations of major towns can be used in analyzing the free customers' locations, instead of the location of the hypermarkets and alternative stores. Figure 1 is a map of the physical boundary of SPT.

Figure 1. Geographical Marketplace of SPT

In general, SPT is a prolific area for business. There exist many types of business as well as markets, retailers, whole salers, business complexes, petrol stations, and many more. It was found from the literature survey of hypermarket business that SPT is an important place for conducting business, since customers from SPT, as well as SPU and SPS can come to do transactions with the hypermarket or any retailing business. The SPT as a centre of business activity, with all kinds of retailing business faced huge competitions especially to stimulate the recency, frequency and spending amount to their preferred business store.

Figure 2 shows all Hypermarkets and alternative markets in SPT which were included in the spatial data of hypermarket and alternative markets of the geographical marketplace of SPT. The retailing business in SPT is currently facing high competition because it contains a huge number of hypermarkets, supermarkets, minimarkets and alternative stores. At the same time, a high number of traditional markets are operating in the area, as well as public markets, night markets, agro markets, and many more. Overall, the spatial data related to the development of geographical marketplace, include each component of the SCLV model.

3.2 Spatialization of the Postal Address Location

In this project, postal addresses of respondents were acquired to trace their location in the geographical marketplace. Postal addresses of the respondents represented the location of free customers, as they appear in the real marketplace. Basically, the postal address must contain 5 details: number of house; street and or road; residential park or village; postal code; and town/district. In the dBase1V format, these data were placed into 7 fields, and designed with an IdName; Address (no of

house and street and or road); Alias (alternative of address); Postcode; Residential Park/Village; Town; and Districts, as shows in Figure 3 and Table 1.

Figure 2. A Visualization of the Geographical Marketplace of SPT.

Figure 3. Spatial Postal Address of Customer in SPT.

Table 1. Postal Address with Longitude and Latitude.

Address	Alias	Postcode	Residensi	Town	District	Latitude	Longitude
182 Lorong Tenggori 27	Lorong Tenggori 27	13700	Seberang Jaya	Perai	SPT	5.38936310	100.4024764
24 Pintas Sembilang 14	Pintas Sembilang 14	13700	Seberang Jaya	Perai	SPT	5.40177500	100.3996560
2 Tingkat Talang 1	Tingkat Talang 1	13700	Seberang Jaya	Perai	SPT	5.38291500	100.3889960
42 Tingkat Kikik 5	Tingkat Kikik 5	13700	Seberang Jaya	Perai	SPT	5.38993200	100.3805140
52 Lintang Talang 6	Lintang Talang 6	13700	Seberang Jaya	Perai	SPT	5.38204410	100.3901034
58 Tingkat Kikik 6	Tingkat Kikik 6	13700	Seberang Jaya	Perai	SPT	5.38832400	100.3823650
35 Lengkok Kikik 3	Lengkok Kikik 3	13700	Seberang Jaya	Perai	SPT	5.39258300	100.3813370
49 Lorong Perai Utama 4	Lorong Perai Utama 4	13600	Taman Perai Utama	Perai	SPT	5.38539900	100.3802740
22 Lorong Senangin 2	Lorong Senangin 2	13700	Seberang Jaya	Perai	SPT	5.38566400	100.3845820
151 Jalan Mohd Saad	Jalan Mohd Saad	12300	Taman Bagan Jermal	Butterworth	SPU	5.42858400	100.3798910
146 Lorong Melur 14	Lorong Melur 14	12300	Taman Bagan Jermal	Butterworth	SPU	5.43298540	100.3839315
19 Jalan Pangsapuri Emas	Jalan Pangsapuri Emas	12300	Taman Mas	Butterworth	SPU	5.42881200	100.3833140
141 Tingkat Kurau 4	Tingkat Kurau 4	13700	Taman Chai Leng	Perai	SPT	5.38785800	100.3916790
17 Lorong Senangin 1	Lorong Senangin 1	13600	Seberang Jaya	Perai	SPT	5.38471800	100.3856430
39 Lorong Kikik 3	Lorong Kikik 3	13600	Seberang Jaya	Perai	SPT	5.39280600	100.3829030
67 Lorong Kikik 6	Lorong Kikik 6	13600	Seberang Jaya	Perai	SPT	5.39311600	100.3842140

3.3 Integration of RFM to Location

As RFM does not available in spatial format, it is important to understand how RFM can be transformed into spatial form. In fact, the postal address of the individual free customer was used as a point for placing the RFM value. For that, the RFM data were represented as tabular data in DBASE1V format and were placed into spatial postal address, as well as tied to the most preferred choice of hypermarket. Therefore, the spatial join data was used to integrate and spatialize these data.

Before RFM data were jointed with attributes of spatial postal address, the RFM data were converted into Dbase1V format, as shown in Table 2 below. The database contained some columns, as such R, F, M, RFM and RFM Weight. In fact, because RFM is available in a five months' series, in total the five months' data of RFM had been transformed into database format. The data of RFM were modeled by using colored pin points as well as matching them with the spatial postal address of the respondents. The values of RFM differed from each other and they could be identified by location based on the streets and roads.

Table 2. Example of RFM Database

R	F	M	Rfm	Rfmweight	F1	F1	M1	Rfm1
1	3	450.00	422	30	2	3	450.00	422
2	4	450.00	432	33	3	4	500.00	332
5	5	450.00	222	20	4	4	480.00	422
1	5	350.00	412	27	1	5	300.00	412
3	5	500.00	432	33	2	4	500.00	432
5	8	300.00	222	20	4	7	300.00	422
2	7	400.00	422	30	3	7	400.00	322
3	6	400.00	232	23	2	5	350.00	432
2	5	350.00	432	33	3	5	350.00	332
1	7	380.00	423	35	3	5	380.00	353
3	9	400.00	322	25	3	8	350.00	322
1	4	500.00	432	33	1	4	500.00	432
1	6	480.00	422	30	2	5	480.00	422
6	6	450.00	242	26	7	6	400.00	142
3	4	550.00	333	30	4	3	550.00	333

4. DISCUSSION

Basically, each component data of CLV (RFM) would be presented in individual point, based on location of postal address of the free customer. Basically, it was possible to produce four types of maps identified as the Map of Recency and Frequency of Individual Customer (See Figure 4 and Figure 5) and the Map of Spending and Combination of RFM of Individual Customer (See Figure 6

and Figure 7). These specific maps were beneficial in analysing each component of RFM in relation to the spatial attributes and geographical marketplace.

In Figure 4, the recency of purchasing the fresh food is indicated by eight scales, starting from 1 day until 8 days, where each category has its own score. It shows that the minimum score was 1 day with 3 respondents, while the maximum score was 3 days with 118 respondents, meaning that a majority of free customers revisited the hypermarket within 3 days, as the range of the current and previous purchases of fresh food was 3 days.

In addition, for the frequency of purchasing fresh food, as shown in Figure 5 it was arranged in nine scales, starting from 2 times per month, followed by 3 times per month, 4 times per month until 10 times per month, each had a unique score. In fact, the minority score was dedicated to the category of 9 times per month with 9 respondents, while the majority score went to the category of 6 times per month with 99 respondents. The spatial recency and frequency will be discussed in the spatial analysis part later.

Figure 4. Recency

Figure 5. Frequency

For the variable of monetary value of RFM as shown in Figure 6, the spending value of each customer was visualized in sixteen major classes, starting from the lowest value of RM250 per month, followed by RM300 per month until the highest value up to RM950 per month. In fact, for the minimum value, the minimum score was RM 860 with 1 respondent, while the maximum score was RM 550 with 84 respondents. The most of the spending value was RM450, while the average spending, as according to 400 respondents was RM460.00.

By combining R, F, and M variables into a matrix value, the RFM matrix value would be pointed out on the individual location, as shown in Figure 7. In total, there were 35 matrix values, and the minority score was dedicated to values such as 124, 142, 213, and so on with a total of 8 matrixes, scored by 1 respondent each. The majority score was dedicated to matrix 333 and 332 with 52 respondents and respectively.

Figure 6. Monetary

Figure 7. Combination of RFM

RFM can be recategorized, into four major categories. In Figure 8 and Figure 9, the score of RFM Matrix and RFM Weight values were re-categorized into four major classes. For the RFM Matrix value, as shown in Figure 8, the minimum values want to the lower category (122 – 242); middle lower (243-324); middle upper (325 – 344) and top value (345 – 444). From a different point of view, it was possible to visualize the RFM is possible to visualize based on weight value, as calculated by RFM weight formula. The use of weight value was better than RFM score value as before, where it could show RFM in absolute value as well as individual unit.

Figure 8. The Score of RFM Matrix

Figure 9. RFM Weight values

Figure 9 shows RFM based on weight value, where the classes were arranged into categories of 13-21 (lower value), 22-26 (middle lower), 27-31 (middle upper) and 32-40 top value. With reference

to this result and literature review, the bottom category of customer needed more attention from the hypermarket whereby some promotional activities should be done to increase the value. Meanwhile, for the top value, the hypermarket needed to retain the RFM activity among the customers, as well as sustain their relationship.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, modelling the spatial RFM as CLV is important. This was done by integrating the spatial and non-spatial data which was required to obtain the lifetime value of free customers. It is important for sustaining the business performance of both current and future prospects of the business. Besides that, a basic spatial RFM is workable to be applied to other variables such as demographic background. In fact, spatial RFM should be tested with shopping behavior data, as a requirement of the RFM model in a natural setting. Meanwhile, the potential developments of RFM model become critical by using open sources technology such as Apps software, open database, android platform and so on.

Acknowledgments: In this section, we thanks you Universiti Sains Malaysia for funding the research by the RU Graduate Research Grant.

References

- Adams, A.L. (2005). *Find and keep the customers you want: The customer insight mandate*. Chicago: Accenture Inc.
- Ali, N. & Shabn, O.S (2024). Customer lifetime value (CLV) insights for strategic marketing success and its impact on organizational financial performance. *Cogent Business & Management*, 11(1).
- Amendah, E.R., Kohli, A., Kumthekar, N., & Singh, G. (2023). Impact of financial and nonfinancial constructs on customer lifetime value (CLV): US retailer's perspective. *Journal of Relationship Marketing*, 22(3), 1–21.
- Andronikov, S. (2008). Geospatial analysis to enhance business decision making. *Proceeding of 2008 ESRI Business GIS Summit. ESRI Business GIS Summit*. April 27- 30, 2008, Chicago, Illinois.
- Bauer, J., & Jannach, D. (2021). Improved customer lifetime value prediction with sequence-to-sequence learning and feature-based models. *ACM Transactions on Knowledge Discovery from Data*, 15(5), 1–37.
- Bejou, D., Keiningham, T.L., & Aksoy, L. (2007). *Customer lifetime value: Reshaping the way we manage to maximize profits*. New York: The Haworth Press, Inc.
- Bell, S.J. (1999). Image and consumer attraction to intra urban retail areas: An environmental psychology approach. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 6, 67- 78.
- Berger, P.D. & Nasr, N.I. (1998). Customer lifetime value: Marketing models and applications. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 12(1), 17 - 30.
- Berger, P.D., Eechambadi, N., George, M., Lehmann, D.R., Rizley, R., & Venkatesan, R. (2006). From customer lifetime value to shareholder value. *Journal of Serv Res*, 9(2),156 -167.
- Berman, B. & Evans, J.R. (2007). *Retail management: A strategic approach*. New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Bromley, R.D.F, & Matthews, D.L. (2007). Reducing consumer disadvantage: Reassessing access in the retail environment. *International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 17(5), 483–501.
- Carpenter, J.M., & Moore, M. (2006). Customer demographics, store attributes, and retail format choice in the US grocery market. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 34(6), 434-452.
- Ching, W.K., Ng, M.K., Wong, K.K., & Altman, E. (2004). Customer lifetime value: Stochastic optimization approach. *Journal of Operational Research Society*, 55, 860-868.
- Eileen, R. (2008). *Corporate value creation: Customer value 2008 report*. London: CIMA Centre of Excellence.

- Epstein, M.J., Friedl, M. & Yuthas, K. (2008). Managing customer profitability: Determine which customers are most valuable to your organization. *Journal of Accountancy (Business and Industry)*. Harvard Business School: December, 2008.
- Fabel, M., Sonnenschein, M., Sester, A. & Golestan, L. (2008). *Customer energy: The empowered consumer is revolutionizing customer relationships*. Chicago: A.T. Kearney Inc. (Marketing and Communications).
- Fader, P. (2009). Understanding customer lifetime value: Conceptual overview and implementation in excel. *Pre-Conference Workshops. Forecasting Summit 2009*. Hilton in the Walt Disney World Resort, Orlando, Florida. February, 23-25, 2009. Retrieved on March 30, 2009 from <http://www.forecasting-summit.com/pre>
- Gilbert, S.J. (2007). *How do you value a "free" customer?* Research & Ideas. Boston: Harvard Business School.
- Graf, A., & Maas, P. (2008). Customer value from a customer perspective: A comprehensive review. *Journal of Financial Business*, 58, 1-20.
- Gupta, S., & Zeithaml, V. (2006). Customer metrics and their impact on financial performance. *Mark Sci* 25(6), 718 - 739.
- Ha, S.H., & Bae, S.M. (2006). Keeping track of customer life cycle to build customer relationship. In. Li, X., Zaiane, O.R. & Z. Li (Eds.), *ADMA*, 372 – 379, Berlin Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag.
- Hamit, H. (2011). *Customer valuation is a crucial step for businesses*. Stamford: Peppers and Rogers Group.
- Hillier, D. & Karki, R. (2008). *Cost and sustainability: The dual challenge for retailers*. MMR/September 22, 30.
- Janiak, S. (2009). *The age of transformation: A retail outlook for 2009 and beyond*. New York: Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu.
- Libey, D.R. (1998). *Libey on RFM value*. New Jersey: Libey Incorporated.
- Peter, C. (2010). *The 16 business benefits of customer lifetime value*. The Wise Marketer, February 2010.
- Rust, R.T., Lemon, K.N., & Zeithaml, V.A. (2004). Return on marketing: Using customer equity to focus marketing strategy. *Journal of Marketing*, 68,109 -127.
- Wang, Y., Sanguansintukul, S. & Lursinsap, C. (2008). The Customer Lifetime Value prediction. *In Mobile Telecommunications, Management of Innovation and Technology, ICMIT, IEEE 4th International Conference*, 2008, 565-569.